

1 **Phosphatase targeting in Luminal B breast cancer: IMPA2.**

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6 Breast cancer can be positive for expression of a hormone receptor (ESR/PGR/AR) or a growth factor
7 receptor (ERBB2). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to endocrine
8 therapy or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
9 existing drugs that treat luminal A and luminal B disease. Here we utilized whole transcriptome
10 technologies (5, 6) to measure total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with luminal A and
11 luminal B breast cancer. We describe one member of a group of phosphatases up-regulated and
12 differentially expressed in human luminal B breast cancer, IMPA2, as a catalytically available phosphatase
13 and candidate therapeutic target for the adjunctive medical treatment of luminal B breast cancer.
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1 CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human luminal A or luminal B organoids or primary
2 tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with luminal subtype breast cancers with limited exposure to
3 artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet
4 implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in luminal A and
5 luminal B hormone receptor positive disease with rapidity and ease.

6 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
7 transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This
8 includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the
9 primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes,
10 metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell.
11 Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic
12 limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential
13 expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented
14 by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify subtype-specific and metastasis-specific
15 therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such
16 target identified through study of the hormone receptor positive tumor transcriptome: a phosphatase target
17 that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: IMPA2.

18 Results

19 **Figure 1:** IMPA2 is differentially expressed in luminal B breast cancer.

20 I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal B subtype

21 $n=29$ luminal A breast cancer

22 $n=30$ luminal B breast cancer

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203126_at	1.85E-03	-3.26	-1.730432	-1.1080208	IMPA2	5087/29873	83.0

23 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the tumors of humans with luminal A breast
24 cancer or luminal B breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of inositol monophosphate
25 2, encoded by *IMPA2* in luminal B breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of IMPA2 changed
26 more than 80% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose
27 expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change
28 indicating increased quantity of IMPA2 messenger RNA in luminal B subtype tumors, suggesting
up-regulation of IMPA2 during transformation and lineage specification of the breast to the luminal B
breast cancer subtype.

Thus, differential and increased expression of IMPA2 defines the transcriptional landscape of the
luminal B breast cancer subtype in humans.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
tamoxifen and letrozole). We recently used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple
phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and
fortuitously found their decreased expression was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients
with another subtype of breast cancer, HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A multi-kinase approach delivered
in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and
activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).

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Methods

We utilized GSE45827 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in luminal A and luminal B subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).